

Data-driven degradation modeling for batch processes: a case study on heat exchanger fouling

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The performance and efficiency degradation of industrial equipment and assets is inevitable in their life cycles. The assessment of process condition provides information of degradation, and the following optimization of process operations is meant to mitigate the influence of degradation. In some cases, it is necessary to shut down the plant and carry out the maintenance operation for restoration when the degradation reaches a certain degree. Human experience-based maintenance scheduling is not necessarily optimal on account of degradation in production along with other physical and logistical constraints. However, optimal scheduling asks for information about future degradation evolution. Therefore, the development of a predictive degradation model plays a significant role in plant performance optimization in consideration of degradation effects.

In this paper, we present an industrial case study of a batch process; the degradation effect is fouling in heat exchangers which impedes heat transfer and fluid flow during batch production. The degradation increases from batch to batch until the batch reactor is shut down for a scheduled maintenance. That is, there is a periodic pattern in the batch-to-batch data as a result of the degradation. We

Figure 1: heat exchanger fouling evolution in batch process and campaigns

propose a novel data-driven modeling technique for predicting the evolution of a batch degradation key performance indicator (KPI). This method extends existing algorithms (based on partial least squares, PLS) for the treatment of within-batch data to the present batch-to-batch degradation problem. A new “campaign” concept is proposed to structure the batch degradation evolution from batch to batch as Figure 1 illustrates. Furthermore, an unfolding method is proposed to transform the four-dimension data into two-dimension unfolded campaign data for PLS modeling. The campaign-based PLS approach is then applied in the case study, and the missing data estimation method TSR is employed for the degradation prediction. The validation result illustrates the effectiveness of the proposed campaign PLS approach in predicting heat exchanger fouling evolution, and this fouling predictions can provide further information for better production scheduling and maintenance planning.

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